

AMALIY VA FUNDAMENTAL TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI

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Appearance of Ancient Religious Ideas in Material Culture

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Abstract: When our ancestors separated from the animal world due to work and were passing the last stages of their formation as humans (the must phase of the ancient stone age), they began to feel their weakness in the face of the hardships of the struggle for survival and the forces of nature. Therefore, they begin to worship the various natural blessings that are the source of livelihood in their living regions, deifying them in the first vision that they continue to live because of them. In those times, the wonder of nature that attracted them was various animals and wild plants. It is probably for this reason that belief in animals and trees originates in the first religious views of mankind. This has found its place in science under the name of totemism.

Over time, our first ancestors became real people, intelligent, conscious people (Homo sapiens-sapiens in science, Adam and Eve in religious views). In the history of mankind, the period of community living, i.e. seed production, begins. At first, the clan was led by mothers, they were imagined as the divine power and power that ensured the continuation of the clan, and as the deity who gave life to mankind. This occurs in the Upper Paleolithic phase of the Old Stone Age. Thus, the worship of ancestors, the deification of mothers leads to the emergence of religious views called animism, fetishism, ancestor worship in scientific language.

These primitive religious views are well observed in archeological objects, in the funeral rites left by our ancestors. They are found in archeological objects in the form of symbolic deities in the form of various shapes drawn on rocks, animal bones, and figurines.

In the periodization of the history of primitive society, people's views on religious ideas expand during the Mesolithic (Middle Stone Age), Neolithic (New Stone Age) and Eneolithic (Copper Stone Age) stages. These are the processes related to the division of clan communities into small collective networks and collective groups, and during these processes, the unique character and qualities of each collective group were formed. Each collective group honors a certain animal as their totem. Such totemistic religious ideas have become a living tradition in science as zoolatric totems, that is, in the Uzbek phrase, the "nickname" (totemic symbol) of the clan community. The totem of the clan was added to the name of every man belonging to a certain clan.

Such cults are one of the informal, decentralized manifestations of religion, and depending on their historical form, they may have consisted of family or clan cults and tribal cults. They were reflected in stone beads and amulets, family and collective seals belonging to the Eneolithic and Bronze Age and have reached us. Some manifestations of such religious views have been preserved among the people until now. For example, it is said that amulets are worn on a young child's hand, on his head, and on his clothes.

The worship of the spirits of ancestors, which is manifested as a manifestation of primitive religious views, has been proven in science as a separate religious view. It is characteristic of the first patriarchal seed production stage of historical development. The concept that "the spirit of deceased ancestors and clan chiefs protects the descendants from calamities" is the essence of this religious view. The concept that "the spirit is always alive, it supports mankind and shows the right path" is considered the basis of this type of prayer.

The existence of religious concepts such as worshipping the spirits of ancestors in Jarkoton was also proven as a result of research carried out by the Uzbek-German Bactrian expedition in 2002. As a result of the research conducted in the Jarqoton monument, the house belonging to the patriarchal family in the Ark area was completely opened and studied. The studied house consists of 9 rooms, and there is a corridor paved with gravel on both sides. Under the walls, floors and stone pavements of this house, 7 graves from the Jarkoton period were opened and studied. Next to the stone corridor is a separate room, inside the room, in its central part, there is a platform. Researchers say that this room was the prayer room of the patriarchal family. A sculpture of a man's head and neck, and a clay mass representing the belly of a pregnant woman and a round embryo were found in this room.

The sculpture of a man's head is very well preserved, and his hair and beard are depicted in black. The cheeks, nose, and neck are red, the nose is pointed, the mouth is open, and the ears are pointed. The eyes are depicted in a closed position, which may be a statue of a dead person.

The second statue is of a woman with a round belly and a raised abdomen to indicate her fetus. The two preserved hands are placed on his stomach, and two snakes are moving between his hands and his stomach. All parts of his stomach and hands are painted with red paint. There is also a mud mass in the form of 2 embryos in the abdomen. Some parts of the statue of a pregnant woman are painted red and the image of a snake is depicted as a sign of the other world. It is known that in mythology, the color red represents blood, and the snake represents underground theology. In these two statues, i.e. the statue of a dead person and the spirit of the ancestors, it can be said that the protection of the pregnant woman and the babies she is expected to give birth from calamities, that is, the worship of the spirits of the ancestors can be observed archaeologically in the material culture.

In the culture of Sopollitepa, the worship of fire is also in the main place, and it is worth mentioning the altar as a manifestation of fire. A total of 12 altars were found as a result of archaeological research conducted in the monuments of Sopolli culture, and they are divided into two types according to their structure. These are circular altars and square altars.

For the first time, circular altars have been widely distributed in Central Asia since the Eneolithic and Bronze Ages. Circular altars can be found in the construction layer of the Sarazm culture belonging to the Eneolithic period, in the Geoksyur 1, 7 monument, which is considered as a monument of the Eneolithic period of Southern Turkmenistan, and in the first Tulkhor cemetery of the Late Bronze Age in the territory of Southern Tajikistan.

The second type of altars are rectangular and are not spread over a wide area. The fact that two such altars were found in the Jarqo'ton monument also indicates that it was not on a large scale.

A. M. Mandelstam, who conducted many years of research in the territory of southern Tajikistan, found a square-shaped altar in a grave of a man buried in the early Bronze Age Tulkhor cemetery, and found a circle-shaped altar in a grave belonging to a woman. Usually, the circle shape represents the mother earth and the sun in a symbolic sense, while the square shape, from the point of view of that time, represents the four sacred elements of nature - the sun - the heat energy supplier to the earth, fire as its part on earth, land - fertile soil, clean air, water - life can be embodied in one subject of faith. If we approach this issue from a philosophical point of view, the discovery of a round altar in the grave of a woman is celebrated by comparison with Mother Earth and the sun, which shares energy, warmth, warmth, and men as guardians of the sanctity and purity of the earth, fresh air, and water. may have been considered. In recent years, the research work on the Sopolli culture, based on the location of altars and two-chambered hearths, it is recognized that in the early stages of the Sopolli culture, they were the hearth of family fire worship. Even with the appearance of a centralized temple in the Kozali and Molali stages, the visible manifestations of such faith did not completely disappear. In the synagogue, people worshiped the fire as a group and performed various religious rituals and rituals related to this. At the same time, each patriarchal family had its own special family worship altars.

It was found that there are 2 rectangular urns where ashes are kept on the 6th hill of the city of the Jarqoton monument. The depth of one of them is 2 meters, and the interior walls of the device are covered with ash. It was also found that such an urn for storing ashes is in one of the rooms of the Jarkoton temple. According to the structure of this ora, it has an oblong shape, and its depth is 70 cm. The researchers mentioned that these embers were a special place designed to keep the embers burning in the sacred fire until the morning. Since embers are also a part of fire, it may have ensured the eternity of fire and its inextinguishability. The top of the pans was sealed airtight and the embers were kept unextinguished until morning.

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